
78. Gaia's first exoplanets

WITH THE RECENT Gaia Data Release 3 (DR3, 13 June 2022), an abundance of new science is already emerging. While the first two *transiting* planets have recently been reported, based on Gaia photometry (Panahi et al. 2022), I want to look here at the first of Gaia's exoplanet discoveries based on its *astrometry*.

In my essay #19 (10 May 2021) I looked at the overall status of exoplanet discoveries, how Gaia's accurate astrometry can hope to discover many more, and also at the rather troubled history of this (in principle powerful, yet extremely challenging) approach.

To set this in context, let me recall that there are various discovery methods that astronomers have developed in the past three decades – including use of radial velocities, photometric transits, gravitational microlensing, and direct imaging. As of mid-2022, out of more than 5000 exoplanets now known, the transit method has discovered nearly 3500, the majority of these being with NASA's Kepler satellite, operated between 2009–18.

WHILE ASTROMETRY, most notably from space with Hipparcos and Hubble's Fine Guidance System, has confirmed a few exoplanets discovered by other methods, and determined improved orbits for a handful, NASA's exoplanet archive still only lists just one exoplanet system *discovered* by astrometry (Jean Schneider's Extrasolar Planets Encyclopaedia lists a further 14).

This object, DENIS-P J082303.1–491201, was discovered via its 246-day orbital motion using VLT-FORS2 imaging by Sahlmann et al. (2013). The host is a low-mass (0.07 solar mass) 'ultra-cool' L dwarf at a distance of just 20 pc, while the 'planet' itself weighs in at a hefty 28 Jupiter masses. Whether it is best considered a planetary system, or the low-mass tail of a stellar binary, is perhaps open for debate.

But with very accurate astrometry, exoplanet discoveries should flow in abundance. But it must be accurate! Even space astrometry with Hipparcos, at the level of 1 milli-arcsec, was demonstrably insufficient to reveal the stellar reflex motion of planets orbiting main sequence stars like our Sun, even within 10–20 pc.

USING THE BEST estimates of exoplanet occurrences, and detailed simulations of the Gaia instrument and its sky scanning, some 20 000 long-period Jupiter-mass planets could be discoverable out to 500 pc for the nominal 5-yr mission (including some 1000–1500 around M dwarfs out to 100 pc), rising to 50–70 000 for a 10-yr mission (e.g. Perryman et al. 2014). In a stroke, astrometry could become the most powerful discovery method in astronomers' current arsenal (assuming that the instrument can be appropriately calibrated).

GAIA DATA RELEASE 3 is in two parts: Early Data Release 3 (EDR3, 3 December 2020), and the full Data Release 3 (DR3, 13 June 2022). As described in my essay #10, both use only observations between July 2014 and May 2017, i.e. a period of 34 months (compared with 14 months for DR1, and 22 months for DR2).

I have summarised the huge amount of new information in Data Release 3 in essay #77. Here I will concentrate on the processing of non-single stars and, in particular, the very first results on exoplanet astrometry.

BINARY AND MULTIPLE stars are ubiquitous throughout our Galaxy. Their census and characterisation is important for deriving certain physical properties, and in understanding the processes of star formation and evolution. Companions with masses below the threshold for nuclear fusion comprise the classes of brown dwarfs and, below about 20 Jupiter masses, planets.

Over the past century, binary systems have been discovered through a variety of methods, and they can be loosely classified into visual binaries (where both components are 'visible'), astrometric (where the companion's presence is revealed by the photocentric motion), spectroscopic (revealed as orbital variations of spectral lines), or eclipsing (where the light from one component is eclipsed by the orbital motion of the other).

With its combination of unprecedented astrometric and photometric accuracy, Gaia is in a position both to discover, and to parametrise, most of these types, simultaneously and uniformly, in substantial numbers.

BEHIND THE SCENES, Coordination Unit 4 of the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium, today led by Frédéric Arenou, is (as one of the nine data processing coordination units) dedicated to the treatment of three 'special' celestial source types observed by Gaia: non-single stars, solar system objects, and galaxies.

The details are, of course, non-trivial, and the 57-page (400+ author) paper published two weeks ago by Arenou et al. (2022) gives some insight into the complexities. Further details of the astrometric orbit determination in Gaia DR3 are given by Holl et al. (2022).

In the case of non-single stars, the multi-epoch astrometric observations (typically some 40 per object distributed over the 34-month time-span of DR3) are examined, and the solutions organised into four classes: those with measured orbits (whether astrometric, spectroscopic or eclipsing); those whose astrometric motion is (currently) better described using a quadratic or cubic rather than a linear proper motion; those that suggest long-period solutions of spectroscopic binaries; and those that display astrometric (positional) variations due to the variability of one component.

Skipping over the details, the resulting numbers are quite staggering: Gaia DR3 contains about 800 000 solutions with either orbital elements or trend parameters (whether for astrometric, spectroscopic and eclipsing binaries, or some combination thereof).

Of these, some 130 000 are full orbit solutions, while more than 300 000 show non-linear astrometric motion, i.e. indicative of partial orbit coverage. All will be substantially improved in future data releases as more data is included, and as the calibration models improve. And many of the present non-linear solutions will progress to full orbit solutions as the temporal baseline improves.

THE SCIENTIFIC INTEREST of these binary and multiple systems is immense: for example, they can be used to examine multiplicity across the entire Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, to clarify the statistics of white dwarf or brown dwarf companions, to quantify their fundamental properties such as mass and radius, to enable studies of, e.g., orbital period versus eccentricity, and to compare the bountiful results with detailed models of star formation and stellar evolution.

To hint at the improvements that Gaia is achieving, there are a factor of around 40 more astrometric orbit solutions in Gaia DR3 as compared to those in the (heterogeneous) *Sixth Catalog of Orbits of Visual Binary Stars* compiled by Hartkopf et al. (2001). And, reassuringly, almost all the Hipparcos targets with an acceleration (7- or 9-parameter) solution also show some sort of significant proper motion 'anomaly' in Gaia DR3.

I will look here at what these early results are starting to convey about the presence of sub-stellar mass companions, brown dwarfs and exoplanets, in Gaia's survey.

THE CATEGORY OF sub-stellar companions comprises brown dwarfs and planets, the division between the two being a complex topic but broadly and simplistically held to occur at about 20 Jupiter masses. Both have been the target of long-term radial velocity searches over the past 20–30 years. Today, with Gaia DR3, astrometry at last reaches the sensitivity to detect sub-stellar companions in very large numbers. And it enables, for the first time, determination of their 3-d orbital architectures, and true (rather than projected) companion masses.

Various tests and selection criteria by Arenou et al. (2022) currently yield 1843 brown dwarf and 72 exoplanet *candidates*. Of these, only 10 brown dwarfs and 9 exoplanets were previously known from ground-based radial velocity surveys, all with a reasonable agreement between (for example) their inferred orbital periods.

I will ignore here the tricky problem of fully validating these candidates (essentially, ruling out a binary star with similar mass components), and I will defer a discussion of the brown dwarf results to a future essay.

OF THEIR CANDIDATES, Arenou et al. (2022) list just two with *validated* orbits implying the presence of new planetary companions:

- HIP 66074 with $P = 297 \pm 2.8$ d, $e = 0.46 \pm 0.17$, and $a_0 = 0.21 \pm 0.03$ mas, of 7.3 ± 1.1 Jupiter masses; and
- HIP 28193 with $P = 827 \pm 50$ d, $e = 0.07 \pm 0.10$, and $a_0 = 0.25 \pm 0.02$ mas, of 5.3 ± 0.6 Jupiter masses.

Their sub-milli-arcsec semi-major axes are especially noteworthy, with their smallest candidate having $a_1 = 0.14 \pm 0.04$ milli-arcsec (or 140 micro-arcsec).

Amongst their other candidates are NASA's only current astrometric listing DENIS–P J082303.1–491201, along with earlier radial velocity discoveries including GJ 876, HD 114762, HD 162020, and HD 164604. Others add to the very rare class of giant planets orbiting white dwarfs, including WD 0141–675 which, at 9.8 pc, is one of the metal-enriched systems suggestive of the capture of planetary debris (see my essay #73).

The detailed treatment by Holl et al. (2022) includes a number of impressive and compelling examples of the fitted orbits, including HD 114762 (7.15 mag, with $P = 83.74 \pm 0.12$ day, $e = 0.32 \pm 0.04$, and parallax 25.36 ± 0.04 mas) shown here.

I'D LIKE to add my own congratulations to my long-term colleagues, Frédéric Arenou and Berry Holl, and their co-authors, on these spectacular results which hint at the wonderful future for exoplanet science being augmented by Gaia.